

230, 280 (sh) & 340 nm, $\nu_{\max}(\text{Nujol})$ cm^{-1} 1800, 1750, 1630; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) 2. 2, (br.s, 12H, four x-O-CO-CH_3), 7.4 (s, 2H, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$ and $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$). The compound was finally established as 4,4', 5,5', 6,6'-hexahydroxy-diphenic acid dilactone by comparison (co-tlc, ir, uv and colour reactions) with the authentic sample of ellagic acid supplied by Fluka, Switzerland.

The powdered bark (150 g) was boiled with water (1.5l) and the tea coloured extract on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml) gave buff coloured precipitate (18.25 g). It was identified as tannin material by iron perchlorate, stiasny and boiling hydrochloric acid reactions. While boiling the bark with water, enough white particles that separated out, were identified as calcium oxalate by systematic analysis.

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Synthesis of Some 1-Substituted-4-Phenyl-2(3H)-Imidazolethiones and Their Desulphurised Products

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LITERATURE survey shows that 1-aryl substitution in the imidazole ring, in general, induces anaesthetic activity¹. A number of 2(3H)-imidazolethiones are used in clinical practice because of their

pronounced biological activity. 1-Methyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione is about hundred times more active than thiouracil². In view of these facts, we have synthesised fourteen new 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones. These have been further desulphurised to get 1,4-disubstituted imidazoles.

Experimental

Phenacyl bromide was condensed with different aromatic amines to get the corresponding phenacylamines (I). These in turn, were converted into 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones (II) by the method of Norrish and Mckee³. The thiones were desulphurised by Raney Nickel to get the 1-substituted-4-phenylimidazoles (III).

Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 377 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase and nujol mull. The compounds were analysed for carbon and hydrogen on Coleman analyser. All m.p.s were taken by capillary method and are uncorrected.

(A) *Synthesis of phenacylamines (I)*: The phenacylamines were synthesised by condensing phenacyl bromide with different aromatic amines by the known method⁴. The ir spectra of these showed the following characteristic bands.

Ir_{KBr} $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}): 3380-3420 (NH), 1675-1685 (C=O), 1610-1600; 1570-1550; 1510-1500 (C=C); 1340-1350 (C-N); 1220 (C-CO-C).

The m.p. and elemental analysis of the new phenacylamines are given in Table 1.

(B) *Synthesis of 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones (II)*: A mixture of phenacylamine (1 mole), potassium thiocyanate (1 mole) in glacial acetic acid was heated under reflux for half an hour and the imidazolethiones were isolated by following the method of Norrish and Mckee³. Particulars of the compounds are listed in Table 2.

(C) *Synthesis of 1-substituted-4-phenylimidazoles (III)*: 1-Substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione (0.1 mole) was dissolved in absolute ethanol and about (0.4 mole) of freshly prepared Raney Nickel was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. The catalyst was filtered off and this solution evaporated on water bath to minimum. The cold mass was diluted with water to faint turbidity and set aside for 24 hrs, when a crystalline product separated. This was filtered and the mother liquid was allowed to evaporate at room temperature to get further crop of the product. These crops were collected and recrystallised to give pure product. The imidazoles obtained are listed in Table 3. Their structures were assigned on the basis of

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NOTES

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Molecular formula	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
					% C	% H	% C	% H
1.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> -H ₂ CCO-NH-C ₆ H ₄	155	61	71.6	5.9	71.9	6.1
2.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N	<i>m</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	184	76	74.0	5.7	73.9	5.5
3.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N	<i>o</i> -HO ₂ C-C ₆ H ₄	170	74	70.5	5.1	71.1	4.9
4.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	110	68	65.6	4.6	65.5	4.4
5.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON ₂	Pyridyl	140	80	73.5	7.6	73.6	7.5
6.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON	Benzthiazolyl	250	65	80.7	5.8	80.5	5.4

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	Molecular formula	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
					% C	% H	% C	% H
1.	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	<i>p</i> -H ₂ COCHN-C ₆ H ₄	230	70	66.0	4.8	65.1	3.8
2.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	<i>m</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	205	68	67.1	4.4	68.0	3.7
3.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	α -Naphthyl	280	60	75.5	4.6	75.6	4.5
4.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	<i>o</i> -HO ₂ C-C ₆ H ₄	210	66	64.8	4.0	65.2	4.0
5.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	<i>p</i> -H ₂ CO-C ₆ H ₄	255	66	68.1	4.9	68.0	4.8
6.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	170	72	58.7	4.1	57.9	4.9
7.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	-C ₆ H ₅	319-20	70	71.4	4.7	71.3	4.6
8.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	227	72	72.1	5.2	72.5	5.3
9.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ BrS	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	212	62	54.3	3.8	54.6	3.4
10.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ ClS	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	221	71	62.8	3.8	62.7	3.7
11.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	248	56	72.8	5.7	72.7	5.6
12.	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	Pyridyl	136	72	66.4	4.8	66.5	4.8
13.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ ClS	Benzthiazolyl	228	64	58.8	3.9	59.9	3.6
14.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	Cyclohexyl	265	67	69.7	6.9	69.8	7.0

TABLE-3

Sl. No.	Molecular formula	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
					% C	% H	% C	% H
1.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂	<i>p</i> -H ₂ COCHN-C ₆ H ₄	145	53	73.8	5.7	72.8	6.1
2.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂	<i>m</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	270	56	75.9	5.4	74.8	5.4
3.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂	α -Naphthyl	94	50	84.4	5.1	84.3	5.2
4.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	<i>o</i> -HO ₂ C-C ₆ H ₄	155	19	72.7	9.0	71.9	8.7
5.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂	<i>p</i> -H ₂ CO-C ₆ H ₄	189	57	76.8	3.6	76.7	5.4
6.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	180	40	67.6	4.5	68.1	4.2
7.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂	-C ₆ H ₅	248	50	81.8	5.4	81.8	5.5
8.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	154	50	82.0	5.9	81.9	5.9
9.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ Br	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	178	47	60.2	3.6	60.2	3.5
10.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	182	49	70.7	4.3	70.8	4.2
11.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	165	50	72.8	5.7	72.7	5.6
12.	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂	Pyridyl	96	50	76.0	4.9	76.0	4.8
13.	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	Benzthiazolyl	91	60	69.3	3.9	69.2	3.8
14.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂	Cyclohexyl	190	57	79.6	7.9	79.5	8.1

elemental analysis and ir spectra⁶. The $\nu_{\max}$ assigned to different characteristic bands⁶ are:

IR_{KBr} $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹): 1455-1600 (C-C phenyl stretching and characteristic for five membered heteroaromatic ring^{7,8}); 1655-1680 (C=C); 3050-2950 (C-H); 675-825 (CH out-of-plane); 1020 (CH-in-plane).

Antithyroid screening of 1-substituted-4-phenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones is in progress and the results will be published separately.

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